

The impact of intercropping, tillage and fertilizer type on soil and crop yield in fruit orchards under Mediterranean conditions: A meta-analysis of field studies

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Intercropping
Cover crops
Tillage
Fertilizer
Orchard

ABSTRACT

A meta-analysis specially based on tree crops was conducted to evaluate the changes in soil organic carbon (SOC), soil N and P, and crop yield in a Mediterranean climate, which are affected by: (i) management practices (crop diversification, tillage, fertilization); (ii) environmental characteristics, such as soil clay and climatic variables; and (iii) study length. The aim of this study was to assess the benefits of crop diversification, conservation tillage (minimum tillage/no-tillage) and organic fertilization as alternatives to intensive conventional mono-cropping in field studies. All the diversified systems and conservation tillage systems and the use of organic fertilizers induced positive effects on SOC. The highest response in SOC was achieved by the growth of permanent crops in the alleys. Soil N showed a similar trend to that of SOC, but the effect of no-tillage was not significant compared to conventional tillage. No significant effect was observed in soil P except for the cultivation of permanent crops in the alleys, which had a negative effect. No effect was observed in tree crop yield due to the growth of alley crops, conservation tillage or organic fertilization. However, the response of crop yield was related to the specific climatic conditions of each region, with possible negative effects in warm and dry areas. Overall, the use of intercropping, conservation tillage and organic fertilization led to improvements in soil quality and fertility and maintenance of a ground cover that can protect soil. However, to avoid possible negative effects on soil P and N availability, the growth of annual alley crops with minimum tillage is suggested instead of permanent crops with no-tillage, especially in dry and warm areas. Our results also suggested that the soil properties evaluated were not the main drivers of long-term yield variability.

1. Introduction

The Mediterranean climate is characterized by warm and rainy winters and hot and dry summers, with frequent, heavy, short rainfall events mainly in autumn. This climate is characteristic of the Mediterranean basin and parts of California, Chile, South Africa and south-western Australia. These conditions lead to water scarcity and soil erosion in the absence of ground cover (García et al., 2005). Perennial crops, such as almond, olive, citrus or grapevines, represent ~16% of the agroecosystems in the Mediterranean area (FAO, 1998), with great economic importance (Olesen and Bindi, 2002).

As in other parts of the world, intensive tree cultivation in Mediterranean soils frequently causes land degradation by depletion of soil organic matter (SOM), erosion, and also, under irrigation farming, soil and water pollution (Almagro et al., 2016; Ibriki et al., 2015; Parras-Alcántara et al., 2016). Mono-cropping can intensify these

environmental problems due to the presence of a large bare soil surface, with added economic threats owing to the low resilience to variability in prices, markets, climate and pests/diseases due to the dependence on a single crop (Barnes et al., 2015). In view of these environmental and economic problems arising from the current mono-cropping and high-input systems used in woody crops, there is now a growing emphasis on crop diversification and optimized use of resources, including with the production of food, feed or industrial products that contribute to long-term sustainability of the agroecosystems and climate change mitigation and adaptation (Li et al., 2019; Rosa-Schleich et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2019). In pre-industrial rural communities, orchards were commonly multi-functional, but they gradually evolved as a result of farm mechanization and increasing intensification towards monocultures that in the late 20th century have become industrial crops dependent on external inputs (Infante-Amate and de Molina, 2013).

Soil health is defined as the continued capacity of soil to function as

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2019.102736>

Received 15 May 2019; Received in revised form 24 October 2019; Accepted 28 October 2019

Available online 25 November 2019

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a vital living ecosystem that sustains plants, animals, and humans (Doran and Zeiss, 2000). Soil health is influenced by agricultural management (Doran and Zeiss, 2000), and therefore, healthy soils are related to high crop yields and low nutrient loss (Congreves et al., 2015). One way to reduce soil and nutrient losses in Mediterranean perennial croplands is the adoption of crop diversification by cultivation of additional crops in the alleys, the use of cover crops or the introduction of livestock. The use of cover crops can enhance the levels of nitrogen, phosphorus and SOM and improve soil microbial populations (Gargouri et al., 2013). Although trees compete for water and nutrients with adjacent crops, sometimes, in the case of intercropping systems with herbaceous crops in the alleys, trees can develop deeper rooting systems, which can obtain water and nutrients from deeper soil horizons and move them to the upper horizons, improving the water availability for shallower-rooted plants (Dawson, 1993; Jose et al., 2004). However, this scenario depends on specific crop species, agricultural management and climate conditions. Cover crops can be used as natural permanent vegetation (spontaneously growing native plants), seeded permanent vegetation (plants introduced by the farmer) and no permanent annual covers that are removed annually with crop residues used as green manure, mulch or forage (García-Orenes et al., 2009; Lozano-García and Parras-Alcántara, 2013; Simoes et al., 2014). Cover crops can protect soil from erosion, increase soil nutrient availability, serve as animal feed, decrease the incidence of pests and diseases, and decrease CO₂ emissions (Aguilera et al., 2013a; Koch et al., 2015; Ramos et al., 2011). Some of the most typical characteristics of Mediterranean orchards are the presence of mono-cropping with long tree spacing, mostly rainfed farming (up to 10 m × 10 m in olive and almond orchards), and frequent tillage to avoid the growth of vegetation in the alleys. Therefore, soil remains bare practically all year (Almagro and Martínez-Mena, 2014; Parras-Alcántara et al., 2016). Thus, a successful strategy to reduce the negative effects of woody cropping systems on soil is to manage tillage. Cover crops and reduced or no-tillage (avoiding bare soil during long periods) have been proposed as management practices to overcome the loss of soil, SOM and nutrients in woody crops (Hugo et al., 2008; Zuazo et al., 2009). A reduction of tillage intensity is normally needed to effectively reduce CO₂ emissions, enhance soil C sequestration and increase soil water availability (Almagro et al., 2017; Wolff et al., 2018). Nonetheless, the effects of cover crops and agricultural management practices can be highly site specific due to soil and climate conditions. In this sense, González-Sánchez et al. (2012), using meta-analysis techniques on carbon sequestration in soil in Spain (Southern Mediterranean region), reported higher C fixation values for native species when compared to sowed cover crops in the alleys of orchards.

Despite the reported advantages, in areas under Mediterranean climate, the reduction in tillage intensity or the use of cover crops or intercropping are not widespread since farmers believe that these kinds of agricultural management practices could negatively affect the water status of the trees (Ramos et al., 2010). In addition, local customs and the beliefs of the farmers mean that they prefer the alleys to have no vegetation, leading to the application of intensive tillage and removal of cover crops, since a field in which the alleys have vegetation has traditionally been considered a “dirty” field (Cerdà et al., 2018, 2017). However, farmers’ perception of the benefits of sustainable management is essential for the success of measures against erosion and soil degradation. Hence, there is a need to spread scientific knowledge to initiate a change towards sustainable orchards. The term “sustainable”, used throughout this article, was coined by the World Commission on Environment and Development of the United Nations in 1987, which defined ‘sustainable development’ as, “Development which meets the needs of the present, without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (Brundtland, 1987). Sustainable management includes three dimensions: social, environmental, and economic (Aznar-Sánchez et al., 2019), although only the environmental dimension was evaluated in this study. Thus, in practice,

sustainable management involves ensuring food security and nutrition, providing social and economic equity, and building and protecting the ecosystem on which agriculture depends (Garibaldi et al., 2017). This can be achieved by adoption, among others, of diversified cropping systems, conservation tillage and organic fertilizers (Aguilera et al., 2013a; Aznar-Sánchez et al., 2019; Garibaldi et al., 2017).

In recent years, some meta-analyses have focused on C sequestration in Mediterranean agroecosystems (Aguilera et al., 2013a; Vicente-Vicente et al., 2016), highlighting the main role of agriculture in climate change adaptation and mitigation, since agriculture and land use change are together responsible for 21–24% of global anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions (Tubiello et al., 2015). Intensive agricultural management can accelerate soil erosion and affects the level of SOC (Chamizo et al., 2017). Other variables studied by meta-analysis have been nitrous oxide emissions, total and available N, soil erosion and microbial content (Cayuela et al., 2017; García-Ruiz et al., 2015; Shackelford et al., 2019). However, the majority of the published studies are based on annual herbaceous crops with no thorough assessment of the effect of crop type or crop diversification on crop yield and soil fertility of woody crops. One of the most important variables to assess in cropping systems is crop yield, which has not previously been assessed under Mediterranean conditions by meta-analysis. Several authors have reported that yield can decrease in young olive trees when cover crops are introduced, although this negative effect on yield disappears in mature trees (Caruso et al., 2011; Gucci et al., 2012; Palese et al., 2014a, 2014b).

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first meta-analysis dealing with the influence of crop diversification on soil properties and crop yields in woody crops in a Mediterranean climate. Furthermore, it is the first attempt to study through meta-analysis the impact of tillage and fertilization on crop yields in Mediterranean orchards. The main novelty of this study is to jointly present results on crop yields and soil dynamics, as these variables are closely interrelated but most studies, and particularly most meta-analyses, do not take both into account. Our study aimed to assess the implication of crop diversification, tillage and fertilization in Mediterranean orchards on soil nutrients, soil organic carbon and crop yield. For this purpose, we compared the use of cover crops in the alleys related to mono-cropping, and the use of organic fertilizers and minimum tillage/no-tillage related to conventional mineral fertilizer and conventional tillage, respectively. To achieve these objectives, we conducted a meta-analysis of 46 papers.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Data collection

Literature searches were conducted in SCOPUS, targeting peer reviewed articles published online through July 2019. The results included 187 experimental treatments from 46 peer-reviewed articles, including the countries of Spain, Italy, France, Portugal, Greece, Turkey, Slovenia, Tunisia, Chile and the United States of America. To obtain the papers listed, we used the keywords “almond OR olive OR citrus OR vineyard OR grapevine OR orchard”, “AND” combinations of the following items: “Mediterranean climate”, “cover crop”, “intercropping”, “alley crop”, “multicrop”, “agroforestry”, “crop yield” and “soil”. Laboratory or greenhouse studies were excluded, and only studies performed in field conditions and carried out in a Mediterranean climate were chosen. When several papers included data from the same experiment, the longest study with the most soil and crop variables was chosen.

A database was compiled with the relevant data extracted for (i) management practices (crop diversification, tillage, fertilization); (ii) environmental characteristics, such as soil clay and climatic variables, (iii) study length and (iv) response variables (total nitrogen (N); available phosphorus (P), soil organic carbon (SOC) and crop yield). Very few articles showed the yield of the alley crops, so we were unable

to perform a meta-analysis on alley crop yields ($n < 8$) (Lee et al., 2019). Consequently, only the tree crop yield is used in this meta-analysis. The database is included as an Excel file in the Supplementary Material, including soil depth used and specific soil characteristics and management. The fruit tree crops used for the study were mostly grapevines (*Vitis vinifera* L.) at 36% of the sample size, olive trees (*Olea europaea* L.) at 34% of the sample size, almond trees (*Prunus dulcis* (Mill.) D.A. Webb) at 15% of the sample size and citrus trees (*Citrus x sinensis* Osbeck, *Citrus x limon* (L.) Osbeck) at 7% of the sample size. We also used other fruit trees, such as avocado (*Persea americana* Mill.), carob (*Ceratonia siliqua* L.), peach (*Prunus persica* (L.) Stokes), chestnut (*Castanea sativa* Mill.) and walnut (*Juglans regia* L.), representing 8% of the total dataset.

To assess the effects of intercropping, tillage and fertilization on soil N, soil P, SOC and yield, we individually studied the following categories (percentages between brackets indicate the frequency of each subgroup within each category):

- A Diversification type, comparing permanent intercropping (PC) (45%) and annual intercropping (AC) (55%) against mono-cropping. Permanent intercropping refers to the maintenance of a permanent cover crop in the alleys, such as aromatics (*Thymus* sp, *Lavandula* sp, *Salvia* sp, *Rosmarinus* sp, *Brachypodium* sp, *Asparagus* sp or natural grass), while annual intercropping means the presence of cover crops in the alleys that are annually harvested or incorporated into the soil. Mono-cropping indicates the presence of the tree crop alone with no other vegetation cover in the alleys (bare soil).
- B Tillage intensity, comparing conservation tillage (no-tillage (NT) (66%) and minimum tillage (MT) (34%)) against conventional ploughing. Minimum tillage involves residue retention in soil since cover crops or weeds are incorporated into the soil.
- C Fertilization type, comparing organic fertilizer (Org) against conventional inorganic fertilizer. Organic fertilizers contain plant or animal-based materials that are either a by-product or an end product of naturally occurring processes, such as humic acids, manure, compost, sludge or crop residues. Inorganic fertilizers are artificially manufactured and contain minerals or synthetic chemicals.

2.2. Statistical analyses

The influence of crop diversification, tillage and fertilization on soil and crop characteristics was studied through meta-analysis. The response ratio was calculated as the effect size unit for each indicator (Aguilera et al., 2013a). This ratio has been widely used for meta-analysis in agricultural studies (e.g., Aguilera et al., 2013a; Lee et al., 2019; Li et al., 2018). The response ratio (RR) was calculated as a proportionate change in the indicator value of the treatment group (sustainable management: intercropping, organic fertilization and no-tillage/minimum tillage) (\bar{X}_{SM}) compared to the pairwise control group (conventional management: mono-cropping, inorganic fertilization and conventional tillage) (\bar{X}_C) (Eq. (1)):

$$RR = \frac{\bar{X}_{SM}}{\bar{X}_C} \quad (1)$$

The natural logarithm of the response ratio was used for the analysis (log (RR)) (Eq. (2)). This transformation linearizes the metric in small samples (Hedges et al., 1999).

$$\text{Log (RR)} = \ln \frac{\bar{X}_{SM}}{\bar{X}_C} = \ln(\bar{X}_{SM}) - \ln(\bar{X}_C) \quad (2)$$

Positive values indicate higher values in the sustainable management, while negative values indicate higher values in the conventional management. In meta-analysis, studies are usually weighted by the inverse of their variance, but this information was not provided in many of the selected studies. We decided to weight observations using the sample sizes to ensure statistical significance by keeping a sufficient

sample size: studies with larger sample sizes were weighted higher during aggregation (Adams et al., 1997). The weighted log (RR) (Wlog (RR)) of management option i was calculated as Eq. (3):

$$\text{Wlog(RR)}_i = \frac{1}{N_i} \sum (\log(\text{RR})_{ij} \times W_{ij}) \quad (3)$$

where N_i is the number of studies for the management i, $\log(\text{RR})_{ij}$ is the log(RR) of management i in study j, and W_{ij} is the weight, calculated as Eq. (4):

$$W_{ij} = \frac{N_i^{SM} N_i^C}{N_i^{SM} + N_i^C} \quad (4)$$

where N_i^{SM} and N_i^C are the sample sizes of the sustainable and conventional management of the management i in study j, respectively (Adams et al., 1997). For the uncertainty analysis, we reported the means and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) of the Wlog(RR). The CIs were constructed by non-parametric bootstrapping (nboot = 10 000). The bootstrapping was only carried out for treatments with $n \geq 8$, as the bootstrap is unreliable when the sample size is too small (Lee et al., 2019). We considered the effect of treatment as significant if the 95% bootstrap CI did not overlap with zero (Lee et al., 2019).

C sequestration rate was calculated according to Eq. (5):

$$\text{C sequestration rate} = \frac{(C_t - C_i)}{t} \quad (5)$$

where C_t and C_i are SOC stocks (Mg C ha^{-1}) at the end and at the beginning of the experiment, respectively, and t is the duration of the experiment (years). In most cases, data on initial SOC content were not available, and so they were equalled to SOC stocks in the conventional treatment. This is justified because only comparisons performed under similar soil and climatic conditions were selected for the analysis, and we focused only on the relative performance of sustainable management versus conventional management (Aguilera et al., 2013a). Most articles did not show SOC stocks, so they were calculated as indicated in equation 6:

$$\text{SOC stock} = d \rho \text{ SOC}$$

where d and ρ are soil depth (m) and bulk density (Mg m^{-3}) in the soil Ap horizon, respectively. For those studies not showing d or ρ , we could not calculate the SOC stock. We could not assess the effect of fertilization on C sequestration rate since very few studies dealing with organic fertilizers and SOC included the bulk density.

Correlations and regressions between Wlog(RR) of SOC, N, P and yield and the variables soil clay, mean annual temperature, mean annual precipitation and study length were carried out to assess the effect of these environmental variables and the length of study on the response rate of the analysed properties. Statistical analyses were performed with the software IBM SPSS Statistics 24.

3. Results

3.1. Influence of crop diversification

Both annual and permanent intercropping were associated with a significant increase in SOC compared to mono-cropping (Fig. 1a). SOC was slightly higher in PC systems than in AC systems, with a mean Wlog (RR) of 0.33 and 0.17, respectively. On average, C sequestration rate also increased by $0.43 \text{ mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ in AC and $1.01 \text{ mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ in PC, with 60% and 71% of studies showing a positive rate (Fig. 1b). The growth of annual crops had no significant effect on soil N, although 71% of values observed were positive, with a mean Wlog(RR) of 0.11. The growth of permanent alley crops was associated with a significant increase in N compared to mono-cropping, with a mean Wlog(RR) of 0.36 (Fig. 2a). The growth of AC had no significant effect on soil P. The mean of Wlog(RR) for P was negative (-0.20), with 67% of studies

Fig. 1. Effects of intercropping, conservation tillage and organic fertilization on soil organic carbon (shown as weighted log response ratio: Wlog(RR)) (A) and differences in Carbon sequestration rates with conventional management ($\text{Mg C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) (B). The “ \bar{x} ” denotes the mean, and the horizontal bar represents the confidence interval at 95%. The number below each bar indicates the size of the sample. AC: annual crops in intercropping; PC: permanent crops in intercropping; MT: minimum tillage; NT: no-tillage; ORG: organic fertilization.

showing a negative effect (Fig. 2b). PC systems showed a significant detrimental effect on soil P compared to mono-cropping, with a mean Wlog(RR) of -0.21. Nevertheless, 50% of the studies showed a positive, but very small, effect of PC on soil P, so the mean Wlog(RR) was negative, owing to the high weight of the studies showing a negative effect. Crop yield was not affected by intercropping compared to mono-cropping, with 42–45 % of the studies showing positive effects (Fig. 3).

3.2. Influence of conservation tillage

Both MT and NT were associated with a significant increase in SOC compared to conventional tillage (Fig. 1a). There was high overlapping in the response ratio between MT and NT, with Wlog(RR) = 0.28 and 0.26 for MT and NT, respectively. On average, C sequestration rate also increased by $1.54 \text{ mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ in MT and $1.40 \text{ mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ in NT, with 75% and 78% of studies showing a positive rate, respectively (Fig. 1b). MT significantly increased soil N compared to conventional tillage (Wlog(RR) = 0.21). However, NT systems had no significant negative effect on N compared to conventional tillage, with Wlog

Fig. 2. Effects of intercropping, conservation tillage and organic fertilization on soil nitrogen and available phosphorus (shown as weighted log response ratio: Wlog(RR)). The “ \bar{x} ” denotes the mean, and the horizontal bar represents the confidence interval at 95%. The percentages at the right represent the proportion of observations with Wlog(RR) > 0. The number next to each bar indicates the size of the sample. AC: annual crops in intercropping; PC: permanent crops in intercropping; MT: minimum tillage; NT: no-tillage; ORG: organic fertilization.

(RR) = 0.09 (Fig. 2a), although 71% of the studies showed a positive effect. Tillage systems had no significant effect on soil P (Fig. 2b) or crop yield (Fig. 3). However, 78% and 36% of studies showed a positive effect on soil P for MT and NT, respectively.

3.3. Influence of organic fertilization

Organic fertilization was associated with a significant increase in SOC and N compared to inorganic fertilization (Figs. 1a and 2 a). This increase was higher for SOC (Wlog(RR) = 0.20) than for N (Wlog(RR) = 0.14). The use of organic fertilizers did not significantly affect soil P, with 50% of studies showing a positive effect (Fig. 2), or yield, with 67% of studies showing a positive effect (Fig. 3) compared to

Fig. 3. Effects of intercropping, conservation tillage and organic fertilization on crop yield (shown as weighted log response ratio: $Wlog(RR)$). The “ \bar{x} ” denotes the mean, and the horizontal bar represents the confidence interval at 95%. The number below each bar indicates the size of the sample. The percentages at the right represent the proportion of observations with $Wlog(RR) > 0$. AC: annual crops in intercropping; PC: permanent crops in intercropping; MT: minimum tillage; NT: no-tillage; ORG: organic fertilization.

inorganic fertilizers. These results indicate that most studies showed positive effects of organic fertilization compared to inorganic fertilization.

3.4. Influence of soil clay, climate and length of study on the studied properties

The response ratios calculated for SOC, N and P were not significantly correlated with clay, temperature or precipitation. However, the response ratios for crop yield showed significant negative correlations with soil clay ($R = 0.60$; $P < 0.01$) and temperature ($R = 0.36$; $P < 0.05$), and a positive correlation with precipitation ($R = 0.35$; $P < 0.05$) (Fig. 4). The experimental length of the different studies was not significantly correlated with any of the studied response ratios ($P > 0.05$).

4. Discussion

4.1. Changes in soil organic carbon and nutrients with intercropping, conservation tillage and organic fertilization

Mediterranean orchards can provide many ecosystem services, such as food production, biodiversity or climate change mitigation (Aguilera et al., 2013b; Lee et al., 2019). However, they are influenced by socioeconomic factors, such as subsidies, farm mechanization, permanent accessibility to fertilizers, government policies, international agreements and farmers’ training, that have led overall to intensive monocropping systems. This cropping system may compromise long-term sustainability owing to soil degradation and loss by intensive tillage and maintenance of bare soil in the alleys during the entire growing season (Almagro et al., 2016; Almagro and Martínez-Mena, 2014; Parras-Alcántara et al., 2016). The overall absence of cover crops and the intense tillage in Mediterranean orchards is related to farmers’ perceptions about competition with the cash crop for nutrients and especially water, and the traditional belief that a “clean” and “tidy” orchard must always be free of vegetation except for the trees (Cerdà et al., 2018, 2017; Ramos et al., 2010). This perception is magnified during the pronounced dry season, a characteristic of the Mediterranean climate, which causes long periods of water stress due to potentially higher

Fig. 4. Relationship between the weighted natural logarithm of the response ratio of crop yield $Wlog(RR)$ and soil clay (A), mean annual temperature (B) and mean annual precipitation (C).gr4

levels of evapotranspiration than precipitation in many areas (Almagro and Martínez-Mena, 2014; Guzmán et al., 2019; Pérez-Álvarez et al., 2015; Sastre et al., 2018; Zornoza et al., 2018). However, the combination of soil degradation and climate change can increase the vulnerability of the Mediterranean orchards and therefore their long-term sustainability, compromising the economy depending on them (Dono et al., 2016; Rocamora-Montiel et al., 2014). As a consequence, actions are needed to revert the current land degradation trends through adoption of sustainable cropping systems that decrease soil loss by erosion, increase soil fertility and biodiversity and secure food production by maintenance of high yields.

Crop diversification and conservation agriculture is now increasingly recognized for its capacity to minimize trade-offs between ecosystem services and maximize synergies between them (Li et al., 2019; Rosa-Schleich et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2019). This meta-analysis helps confirm the overall benefits of alley cropping in orchards that associated with conservation tillage, organic fertilization on soil quality and health, and C sequestration in Mediterranean agroecosystems due to the maintained inputs of SOM, which improve soil structure and fertility and are therefore associated with increased soil biological activity (Álvarez et al., 2007; Bastida et al., 2012; Castro et al., 2008; Ramos et al., 2010; Vignozzi et al., 2019). Although the discussion continues

regarding the most appropriate soil properties or approaches able to indicate soil quality or soil health, SOC and N are two of the most commonly used internationally recognised soil quality indicators owing to the ecosystem services they provide (Zornoza et al., 2015). Therefore, the increases observed in the SOC, soil N and C sequestration rates in this study following the adoption of sustainable cropping systems, associated with high yields, can be used as indicators of soil quality improvement with maintenance of land productivity. This finding aligns with the principles addressed by Letey et al. (2003) to assess soil quality, focusing more on soil use, not function or capacity, as the criteria for attribute evaluation. These results, therefore, should be used to raise farmers' awareness about the strengths of the cropping practices assessed through this meta-analysis, which achieve the combined goals of high crop production, low environmental degradation and sustained use of resources (Letey et al., 2003; Zornoza et al., 2015).

The use of intercropping, associated with conservation tillage, is characterized by minimal soil disturbance, ground cover in the alleys during at least some periods of the crop cycle, improved biodiversity and biological processes in the soil, and the preservation of multiple ecosystem services (Aguilera et al., 2013a; Chamizo et al., 2017; Lee et al., 2019; Taguas et al., 2015). Annual or permanent crops can be grown in the alleys solely to prevent soil erosion and enhance soil quality, water retention, soil nutrients, contribute to weed suppression and attract pollinators and auxiliary fauna, which are especially important effects in desertification-prone Mediterranean agroecosystems (e.g., Almagro et al., 2016; Chamizo et al., 2017; Hernández et al., 2005; Koch et al., 2015; Ramos et al., 2011; Taguas et al., 2015). However, they can also be grown to provide, despite the latter ecosystem services, an alternative crop with economic profitability for the farmer, such as food, feed or industrial products, increasing the resilience of the system to pest/disease incidences and market volatility (e.g., Barnes et al., 2015; Bateni et al., 2019; Cardinael et al., 2015; Hugo et al., 2008; Querné et al., 2017). Most alley crops used in Mediterranean orchards are either natural grasses, cereals, legumes or a mixture of legumes and cereals for environmental benefits or aromatics, such as lavender, sage, rosemary, thyme, alfalfa, fava bean, wheat, barley or asparagus for direct economic profitability (Almagro et al., 2016; Bateni et al., 2019; Cardinael et al., 2015; Chamizo et al., 2017; Hugo et al., 2008; Querné et al., 2017; Ramos et al., 2011, 2010; Taguas et al., 2015). Independent of the final objective of the alley crops, they were shown to have increased SOC and C sequestration rates with permanent or annual intercropping and soil N content in permanent intercropping, contributing to the maintenance of high quality soils.

In our meta-analysis, SOC and N were positively influenced by the presence of alley crops, independent of the orchard type. The presence of permanent vegetation had a more positive effect than the growth of annual crops, mostly for N. Permanent vegetation can enhance SOC and N through the continuous release of root exudates and litter deposition content, contributing to effective C sequestration (Sastre et al., 2018). The growth of annual crops is normally related to bare soil periods with at least minimum tillage. Therefore, annual alley crops have lower potential to increase SOM as much as permanent vegetation, related to the lower C inputs to the soil (Belmonte et al., 2018; Daryanto et al., 2018). When permanent cover crops were used, the P content in the soil did not follow the increasing trend observed with N, which may likely be due to the higher P demands of the permanent vegetation growing in the alleys.

The synergy between intercropping and conservation tillage is associated with physical soil improvement, water conservation and the prevention of increases in CO₂ emissions (Almagro et al., 2016; Simoes et al., 2014). Intensive tillage is applied by farmers to promote soil aeration and water infiltration and to reduce the growth of weeds. However, it can have other drawbacks, such as the destruction of soil aggregates, decreases in soil aggregate stability, damage to soil organisms and an increase in soil vulnerability to erosion (García-Díaz et al., 2018; Gómez et al., 2009; Ruiz-Colmenero et al., 2013). In addition,

intensive tillage may induce oxidation of organic compounds by aerobic microorganisms due to increased aeration, which could result in a loss of SOC and increased greenhouse gas emissions (Palese et al., 2014a, 2014b). Conservation tillage, however, is usually associated with increases in SOC concentrations by decreasing SOM mineralization, which is associated with increases in soil water retention (Almagro et al., 2016; Garcia-Franco et al., 2015). In addition to decreasing aeration and disruption of soil aggregates, this positive effect on soil organic matter due to conservation tillage is also related to the stratification of SOM in different depths, which has been reported to positively affect erosion control and nutrient and water conservation (Hernanz et al., 2009). Despite the absence of differences with regard to NT and MT in SOC, N showed higher values in MT than in NT. This finding can be related to the high soil compaction and sealing that takes place in dry Mediterranean areas when NT is applied as a consequence of the low SOM content, leading to reduced N mineralization rates and the resulting low soil N availability (López-Garrido et al., 2014; Martínez-Mena et al., 2013). Nonetheless, the average value of soil depth in the studies used in this meta-analysis is 19 cm, ranging from 5 to 60 cm (see the database attached as Supplementary Material). The effect of conservation tillage on deeper soil layers, therefore, could not be assessed within this meta-analysis.

The use of organic fertilizers has been proposed to enhance soil quality and carbon sequestration in comparison to inorganic fertilizers (Montes-Borrego et al., 2013; Parras-Alcántara et al., 2015). Moreover, the use of lignin-rich organic fertilizers in fruit orchards can create an organic horizon with high biological activity, which could transfer the organic C to the mineral horizons (López et al., 2014). Our results demonstrate the increase of SOC in orchards with organic fertilizer application compared to inorganic fertilizers. In addition, from a climate change mitigation approach, the addition of organic fertilizers is also related to the reduction in the use of synthetic fertilizers and the GHG emissions related to their production (Aguilera et al., 2013b). However, the growth of permanent crops and conservation tillage resulted in a larger increase in SOC than the addition of organic fertilizers (Fig. 1). Thus, although the replacement of inorganic fertilizers by organic fertilizers is a positive strategy to increase soil organic matter, the adoption of diversified cropping systems with conservation tillage is even more effective. This disparity may be related to the protection exerted by vegetation on the soil, with the release of root exudates, accumulation of litter, and incorporation of crop residues into the soil as green manure in the case of annual crops.

It is interesting to highlight that the response ratios of the different soil properties analysed were not correlated with the climatic variables of mean annual temperature and mean annual precipitation. Thus, these results suggest that the response of SOC, soil N and soil P to management practices is not highly dependent on the specific climatic conditions of the region, with positive effects of intercropping, conservation tillage and organic fertilization on soil quality occurring independent of the specific heat or aridity of the area. Although no significant effect of the experimental length of study was observed in our analysis, this lack of effect could have been influenced by the relatively small quantity of papers showing long-term results. Only 40% of the experimental treatments had an experimental length > 5 years, and only 13% of them had an experimental length > 10 years. Thus, there is a need for publication of studies dealing with the long-term effect of intercropping, conservation tillage and organic fertilization in Mediterranean orchards to assess their trends over time.

4.2. Changes in tree crop yield with intercropping, conservation tillage and organic fertilization

Food production is the primary function of orchards, but unsustainable cropping systems and climate change threaten high crop yields in Mediterranean climates (Iglesias et al., 2011). Our results showed a potential for alternative cropping systems with no negative

effects on the cash crop yield, but with benefits for soil quality and biodiversity. Despite farmers' perceptions about reduced crop yield with the implementation of alley crops, conservation tillage or organic fertilizers, these practices have not provided negative effects on crop yields compared to conventional systems. This result supports that alley crops, no-tillage or reduced tillage and the incorporation of nutrients as organic amendments affect soil structure and fertility positively, with higher availability of nutrients and water retention due to increased SOM and soil aggregation (Almagro et al., 2017; Daryanto et al., 2018; Montanaro et al., 2017). Moreover, the presence of a vegetation cover in the alleys of orchards can provide habitat for arthropod predators and parasitoids, which promote biological control by feeding on pests and microorganisms (Paredes et al., 2015).

Alley crops showed no negative overall effect size on crop yield. However, it is true that some studies used in this meta-analysis detected that the growth of annual crops and mostly permanent crops can have negative effects on the tree yield (e.g., Atucha et al., 2013; Hernández et al., 2005; Klodd et al., 2016; Ripoché et al., 2011; Taguas et al., 2015). Furthermore, while climatic conditions were not correlated to the response ratio of soil properties to the analysed management practices, they were related to the response ratio of the crop yield. Our results showed that the response ratio of crop yields tended to be lower in those areas with higher temperature and lower precipitation compared to the control (Fig. 4), and therefore, there were lower increases or even decreases in crop yields compared to the conventional systems. Therefore, farmers' perception that alley crops can decrease soil moisture and consequently compete with tree crops for water seems to be important in those areas with higher aridity and warm temperatures. As a consequence, to avoid the excessive competition with alley crops which can negatively affect the cash crop yield, the use of annual crops can be used instead of permanent crops that need to be efficiently managed. The growth of annual crops allows the management of the ground cover to remove the secondary crops in the critical periods when competition for water or nutrients is high, such as summer or when the fruit is forming, avoiding negative effects on yields (Daryanto et al., 2018; Palese et al., 2014a, 2014b). The nutrient requirements of the trees are higher when the fruit is forming, so the early elimination of competition for nutrients by alley crop removal at this critical stage should be encouraged (Palese et al., 2014a, 2014b). Furthermore, it has been reported that due to their deep and fibrous rooting systems, species from the Poaceae family generally result in higher evapotranspiration rates than legumes (Duval et al., 2016), so legumes could be good candidates for alley cropping in dry areas. According to our results, a limit of 470 mm of mean annual precipitation and a mean annual temperature of 15.5 °C may be suggested as thresholds for which caution should be exercised by farmers to avoid negative effects on tree crop yields (Fig. 4). A thorough management of the alley crops in regions with temperatures over and precipitation under this threshold should be implemented with the removal of annual crops during those critical periods when there can be competition with the cash crop, as discussed above.

Conventional tillage is usually performed to remove weeds, and thus avoid water and nutrient competition, and to incorporate fertilizers and manure into the soil (Palese et al., 2014a, 2014b). However, conservation tillage showed no negative effects on crop yields because the increase in SOM can positively influence water storage capacity and the availability of nutrients in soil (Almagro et al., 2016; García-Franco et al., 2015). However, after assessing all effects on crop yields with regard to no-tillage or minimum tillage, we have found that, although no overall negative effects have been detected under minimum tillage in the various studies, under arid and semiarid conditions, no-tillage may have negative effects on crop yields in rainfed orchards, especially in almond and olive groves (De Leijster et al., 2019; Hernández et al., 2005; Martínez-Mena et al., 2013; Vignozzi et al., 2019). This negative impact can be related to the high soil compaction and sealing due to low SOM content, leading to a lack of sufficient soil aeration and

reduced N mineralization rate (López-Garrido et al., 2014; Martínez-Mena et al., 2013). This soil compaction may induce N limitations in the crop, hamper root development and hinder gas exchange in the roots. Under these conditions, minimum tillage is recommended to break soil compactness, unless until SOM is increased so that no compaction is produced (López-Garrido et al., 2014; Martínez-Mena et al., 2013).

Crop yield differences between organic and conventional farming have been reported to average 20% (Lee et al., 2019), a difference that is normally explained by the difficulty of managing soil P in organic systems (Oehl et al., 2002). The lack of a significant negative effect of organic fertilization compared to inorganic fertilization on crop yield might therefore be related to the absence of a negative influence of organic fertilization on available P in soil (Fig. 2). Soil available P content was significantly correlated with crop yields using all the experiments included in this meta-analysis ($R = 0.34$; $P < 0.01$), highlighting the importance of soil P on land productivity. Thus, under current management practices in Mediterranean orchards, nutrients such as N and P are not reduced with the adoption of organic fertilizers, while also maintaining the same yields. Therefore, increasing soil organic matter leads to no economic losses expected for farmers in addition to positive effects on soil quality.

Texture is one of the most important variables of soil because it can affect gas exchange, thermic conductivity, aggregates and root growth. Moreover, clay enhances water retention in soils and has a high capacity for cation exchange (Nguyen and Marschner, 2014). Therefore, soils with low clay content tend to be associated with low availability of nutrients and water for plant growth (Zornoza et al., 2015). Our study has detected that soil clay content can influence the response of crop yield to intercropping, conservation tillage and organic fertilization since soils with lower clay content were related to higher response ratios in crop yield than soils with high clay content (Fig. 4). Thus, in soils with low clay content and the associated lower potential fertility, the effects of intercropping, conservation tillage and organic fertilization are more evident than in soils with higher potential fertility, likely associated with the improvements in soil structure and fertility by the adoption of these practices, as discussed in Section 4.1.

It is important to highlight that the consulted articles only reported data on the tree yield, without specifications about complementary yields with cultivation of secondary crops in the alleys (intercropping systems) nor the effects on the land equivalent ratio (LER). LER is used to characterize land use efficiency by representing the sum of the relative yields in an intercrop compared to the sole crop yields. When $LER > 1$, the intercropping system is advantageous since it produces more yields with the same land requirements (Mead and Willey, 1980). Thus, for the study of yield from all crops in the orchard, the analysis of LER is needed to conclude that intercropping has actual detrimental effects on crop yield since the overall productivity of the land could be enhanced. In this sense, Bai et al. (2016) reported LERs of 1.34, 1.44 and 1.33 in mixed systems between rainfed apricots and peanuts, millet and sweet potato, respectively, in a semiarid area of China. Arenas-Corraliza et al. (2018) also reported an $LER > 1.34$ in a hybrid walnut silvoarable system intercropped with wheat and barley in Spain. These authors concluded that intercropping systems may improve the productivity of rainfed agriculture more than sole pure plantations, especially when a drought adapted crop is used. However, it is true that many cover crops are just grown for environmental benefits, so the LER concept should be adjusted for the value of the product in orchards to make sense as a management decision-making criterion.

Social services were not assessed in this meta-analysis. However, the adoption of diversified cropping systems in Mediterranean orchards, with high diversity and aesthetic value, can attract tourism to rural areas and provide an opportunity for farmers to diversify their incomes (Brandth and Haugen, 2011). For example, almond and olive groves intercropped with flowers such as legumes or aromatics in the alleys (Belmonte et al., 2018; Hugo et al., 2008; Novara et al., 2019;

Rodrigues et al., 2015) can increase the aesthetic value of the landscape, attracting tourism and enhancing the profitability of the agroecosystems, as in the case of the High Provence in France, where lavender has become a tourist attraction (Lorenzini, 2010).

5. Conclusions

The results of our meta-analysis highlighted the overall positive effects of intercropping, conservation tillage (minimum tillage and no-tillage) and organic fertilization on SOC and soil N contents, with general increases compared to mono-cropping, conventional tillage and inorganic fertilization. Nonetheless, the adoption of no-tillage had no positive effect on soil N. The growth of permanent crops in the alleys led to higher increases in SOC and soil N. However, this practice was related to negative effects on available P in the soil. Intercropping, conservation tillage or organic fertilizers had no significant effects on crop yield compared to conventional systems. However, the response of crop yield to these practices was related to the specific climatic conditions of the area, with possible negative effects in regions with low precipitation and high mean annual temperature. Thus, to avoid potential problems with nutritional deficits for crops and water stress, the growth of annual crops in the alleys, together with minimum tillage and organic fertilization seems the best alternative, with increases in soil organic matter and nitrogen content that positively improve soil quality and make the agroecosystem more resilient to drought and erosion events, with no negative effects on tree crop yield. The incorporation of such cropping systems and practices in policy measures could provide a meaningful contribution to securing the long-term soil quality of Mediterranean orchards. Our results also suggested the soil properties evaluated were not the main drivers of long-term yield variability.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the European Commission Horizon 2020 project Diversifarming [grant agreement 728003]. Raúl Zornoza acknowledges the financial support from the Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities through the “Ramón y Cajal” Program [RYC-2015-18758].

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